

Dushivishajanya Indralupta (Alopecia Barbae): A case successfully treated with Ayurvedic Management

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ABSTRACT: *Indralupta* (Alopecia Areata) is an autoimmune disease characterized by hair loss that can be correlated with *Indralupta* in Ayurveda. While the condition commonly affects the scalp, it can also manifest in the beard region. Ayurveda attributes this to the vitiation of *Tridosha* and *Rakta*. This case report discusses the management of a 23-year-old male diagnosed with *Dushivishajanya Indralupta* (toxic origin alopecia) involving a circular patch in the beard. The patient was treated with a combination of *Shamana* (palliative internal medication) and *Shodhana* (purificatory *Pracchana Karma*) therapies. Significant improvement, including the appearance of tiny hairs, was noted within 10 days of treatment.

KEYWORDS: *Indralupta*, *Dushivishajanya*, *Pracchana Karma*, *Dushivishari Agada*, Alopecia Barbae.

INTRODUCTION

Alopecia areata is an autoimmune disease characterized by hair loss on the body, especially on the scalp, without any clinical inflammatory signs. Its prevalence in the general population is estimated at 0.1-0.2%. In Ayurveda, this condition is described as *Indralupta*.⁽²⁾

According to *Acharya Sushruta*, *Pitta* along with *Vata* involves the roots of the hair (*Romakoopa*) causing hair fall, while *Shleshma* (Kapha) along with *Shonita* (Blood) obstructs the channel of *Romakoopa*, leading to the stoppage of hair regeneration. Conventional treatments like corticosteroids often have limitations. This case highlights the efficacy of Ayurvedic management in a patient diagnosed with *Dushivishajanya Indralupta*, focusing on detoxification (*Vishaghna*) and hair nutrition.

CASE REPORT

A 23-year-old male patient, visited the *Vishachikitsa* (Toxicology) Department at Rani Dullaiya Smriti Ayurved P.G. College and Hospital, Bhopal.

- **Chief Complaints:** Loss of hair from the beard in a circular patch from last 3 months, accompanied by itching in that patch at night. There was no discharge from the patch.
- **Patient History:**
 - No history of Diabetes Mellitus, Thyroid dysfunction, or Hypertension.
 - Pt. had a history of usage of chemical- based hair products since last 2-3 years. Also, he had a history of intake of large amount of oily, spicy foods (*virudha ahara*) from last 10 years.
- **General Examination:**
 - **Pulse:** 98/min.
 - **Blood Pressure:** 130/90 mmHg.
 - **Weight:** 65 kg.
 - **SpO₂:** 98%.
- **Local Examination:** A circular patch of hair loss was observed in the beard region.

Diagnosis

The patient was clinically diagnosed as *Dushivishajanya Indralupta* (Alopecia caused by cumulative latent toxins).

Treatment Protocol

The treatment plan involved both *Shamana* (internal medicine) and *Shodhana* (external procedures)

Table 1: Prescribed Internal Medicines

Medicine	Dose	Anupana (Vehicle)	Therapeutic Indication
Tab. Dushivishari Agada	2 tablets BD	Honey	Anti-toxic formulation to neutralize <i>Dushivisha</i> .
Tab. Asthiposhak Vati	2 tablets BD	Water	Calcium supplement to strengthen <i>Asthi</i> (bone) tissue.
Tab. Bhumyamalaki	2 tablets BD	Water	Liver support and <i>Pitta</i> pacification.
Bhringarajasava	15 ml BD	Equal Water (After food)	<i>Keshya</i> (hair tonic) and metabolic enhancer.

Table 2: External Applications and Procedures

Procedure/Medicine	Instructions	Purpose
Pracchana Karma	Multiple sittings (e.g., 08/10/25, 23/10/25, 7/11/25, 22/11/25)	Bloodletting/scraping to remove local obstruction in hair roots.
Bhringaraj Churna	Local Application (Lepa)	Hair growth promoter.
Bhringaraj Oil + Bakuchi Oil	Local Application (L/A)	<i>Bakuchi</i> is specific for skin lesions; <i>Bhringaraj</i> promotes growth.
Triphala Kwatha	For <i>Prakshalana</i> (Washing) twice daily	Antimicrobial wash to purify the local area.

Observations and Results

The patient was monitored over multiple visits. The progression of the treatment is recorded below:

Table 3: Timeline of Observations

Date	Day	Observations & Procedures
07/10/2025	Day 1	Diagnosis: <i>Dushivishajanya Indralupta</i> . Vitals: BP 130/90, Pulse 98. Plan: <i>Pracchana Karma</i> advised.
08/10/2025	Day 2	Procedure: 1st sitting of <i>Pracchana Karma</i> performed successfully.
23/10/2025	Day 15	Follow-up: Patient reported relief. 2nd sitting of <i>Pracchana Karma</i> done. Improvement: Presence of tiny hair noted in the patch. Symptom: Itching persisted (++) . Action: Added Bhringaraj Oil + Bakuchi Oil.

Date	Day	Observations & Procedures
07/11/2025	Day 30	Procedure: 3rd sitting of <i>Pracchana Karma</i> done. Vitals: BP:110/70, Pulse 72. Action: Continued all meds; added <i>Triphala</i> kwatha wash.
22/11/2025	Day 45	Procedure: 4th sitting of <i>Pracchana Karma</i> done. Patient got much relief from the symptoms many small hair follicles seen in the patch area. Vitals: BP:120/80, Pulse:78. Action: Dushivishari agada stop & rest all medication continued for more 2 weeks.

BEFORE TREATMENT

PROCEDURE PRACCHAN KARMA FOLLOWED BY BRINGRAJ CHURNA LEPA

AFTER TREATMENT

DISCUSSION

Acharya Charaka mentions that *Tejas* (body heat/Pitta) involving *Vatadi Dosha* reaches the scalp and results in *Indralupta*. The obstruction of hair roots (*Romakoopa*) by *Kapha* and *Rakta* prevents regrowth.⁽⁵⁾

In this specific case, the diagnosis *Dushivishajanya* implies the involvement of weak, latent toxins (*Dushivisha*) affecting the *Rakta Dhatu*.

1. **Dushivishari Agada** was selected to eliminate these circulating toxins, addressing the root cause. ⁽³⁾
2. **Asthiposhak Vati** was administered based on the principle that hair (*Kesha*) is the *Upadhatu* (byproduct) of *Asthi* (bone); strengthening bone tissue supports hair growth.
3. **Pracchana Karma (Scraping)**: Similar to the *Gunja* scraping mentioned in classical texts, *Pracchana* removes the obstruction (*Avarana*) at the hair root caused by vitiated *Kapha* and *Rakta*, facilitating regrowth
4. **Local Application**: The use of *Bhringraj* and *Bakuchi* oils provides direct nourishment to the follicles and treats the localized skin pathology. ⁽⁶⁾

CONCLUSION

The patient, showed positive signs of recovery within the first 10 days of treatment, evidenced by the appearance of tiny hairs in the alopecia patch. The combination of internal *Shamana* therapy (targeting toxins and bone metabolism) and external *Shodhana* (*Pracchana*) proved effective. *Pracchan karma* helped to open up the pores that has been blocked due to *kapha* accumulation at the site. *Bhringraj* has the potency of hair growth, thus local application of *bhringraj lepa* helped in growth of new hairs. ⁽⁷⁾ This supports the Ayurvedic view that removing the blockage at the hair root (*Romakoopa*) and purifying the blood are essential for treating *Indralupta*.

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